

Towards *in situ* de-risking of lunar granular materials handling: Design, manufacture, and initial testing and initial validation of a rotating drum breadboard suitable for vacuum conditions and eventual lunar gravity parabolic flight

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Abstract

As lunar exploration and prospects for commercial exploitation accelerate, understanding regolith behaviour under low gravitational and vacuum conditions is vital for engineering robust In-Situ Resource Utilisation (ISRU) systems. Accurate characterisation of dynamic granular flow properties, such as flow regimes and the dynamic angle of repose of naturally occurring lunar materials within lunar environments, is essential for optimising lunar surface material handling procedures and hardware. Consequently, there is a requirement for dedicated lunar payloads capable of generating relevant *in situ* datasets. In previous work, the MULE concept was proposed as a multi-subsystem payload to examine these phenomena directly on the lunar surface. This paper details the initial design and testing of one of the selected technologies—a rotating drum system with integrated video analysis—intended for technology de-risking and comparison against commercial bulk materials testing systems.

The current breadboard iteration (Version A) prioritises rapid FDM 3D-printed components alongside commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) hardware. To ensure data comparability, a study was conducted to evaluate the breadboard's performance against an industry-standard laboratory rotating drum tester (GranuDrum). This work represents a first developmental step toward an experimental platform capable of operating in lunar gravity parabolic flight campaigns and, ultimately, as a lunar payload. Further developments (Version B) will focus on automated sample management via a dosing carousel to enable high-throughput autonomous operation.

Key findings demonstrate reliable hardware function across operational envelopes extending to free molecular flow vacuum pressures. Results indicate comparability with the commercial rotating drum tester across a range of nine regolith simulant materials. Further operational tests revealed expected distinctions in material behaviour when samples were subjected to thermal pre-treatment or handled under varying atmospheric conditions, confirming the system's sensitivity to environmentally induced rheological changes.

Keywords

Lunar exploration, granular materials, bulk materials handling, dynamic characteristics, dynamic angle of repose, vacuum testing, parabolic flight.

1 Introduction

1.1 Importance of Dynamic Material Handling for Future Lunar Surface Activities

Plans to establish a persistent human presence on the Moon (NASA, 2020; Lin et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2026) rely heavily on the viability of In-Situ Resource Utilisation (ISRU) to source and process raw materials for construction and manufacturing (Azami et al., 2024; Badescu et al., 2012; Bennett et al., 2020; Crawford, 2015; Wang et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2023). Consequently, technologies such as excavation, screening, beneficiation, mixing, and conveying will represent critical nodes in future lunar ISRU architectures (Larson et al., 2010; Just et al., 2020).

While these technologies are mature in terrestrial environments, they cannot be directly transferred to the lunar surface. The unique conditions of the lunar environment - characterised by reduced gravity (1/6g), a hard vacuum exosphere, and the distinctive properties of lunar regolith, such as high angularity, abrasiveness, and cohesiveness - pose substantial engineering challenges for these future endeavours (Shaw et al., 2022; Walyon et al., 2007; Walton, 2012).

1.2 The Need for In-Situ Validation of Material Handling Knowledge

Although terrestrial dynamic bulk material handling is well-studied, current understanding of lunar surface behaviour is largely based on simulation techniques, including parabolic flights, the use of regolith simulants, and numerical modelling

(e.g., Discrete Element Method) (Bui et al., 2009; Pletser, 2015; Pratnekar et al., 2025). However, there remains a critical concern that these results have not yet been validated or calibrated against real lunar environmental data.

This lack of *in-situ* validation creates a knowledge gap that poses a risk of hardware failure or operational inefficiency. Misconceptions regarding lunar granular behaviour could lead to poor performance, such as system clogging, erratic flow rates, or excessive component wear due to unpredicted material friction. To address this, the "Materials Utilisation for a Lunar Economy" (MULE) project was proposed (Pratnekar et al., 2026). The MULE concept outlines a dedicated lunar payload designed to take a "pragmatic approach" to generating *in-situ* datasets, focusing on observing practical material handling subsystems—such as excavation and hopper discharge—directly on the lunar surface to de-risk and calibrate Earth-based simulations.

1.3 Context of the current work: The Rotating Drum Breadboard

The focus of this paper is the design and manufacture of a rotating drum experimental breadboard capable of operating within vacuum chambers and, with further refinement, during reduced-gravity parabolic flight campaigns. The core objective is to develop a system capable of generating relevant dynamic granular material handling data in conditions closely approximating the lunar environment (specifically regarding vacuum pressure and gravity), bridging the gap between terrestrial testing and future *in-situ* datasets (Pratnekar et al., 2026).

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The proposed research is structured in two parts. The present work describes the development and initial testing of the "Version A" breadboard, with the immediate objectives to de-risk mechanical and electrical functionality in vacuum and to demonstrate data comparability with standardised commercial testers (e.g., GranuDrum) (GranuDrum, 2026; Vipin et al., 2024). Future development will iterate this design into "Version B," a fully autonomous, multi-sample system suitable for parabolic flight campaigns and eventual deployment as a lunar surface payload.

2 Justification for the Rotating Drum Breadboard

2.1 Rotating Drums in ISRU Architectures and Granular Materials Characterisation

In future lunar ISRU architectures, rotating drum components will serve as critical nodes within the material handling, transport, and processing chains. Their primary operational roles include:

- **Mixing and Homogenisation:** Ensuring uniform distribution of bulk granular materials for downstream processing.
- **Chemical Reactors:** Functioning as rotary kilns or reactors to facilitate thermal or chemical transitions (e.g., hydrogen reduction of ilmenite).
- **Conveyance:** Utilising cascading or flighted motion to continuously move material through internal processing volumes.

The operational reliability of these stages is paramount. In scenarios where a steady, smooth cascading motion is required for uniform thermal exposure or mixing, unpredicted transitions to higher-energy regimes—such as premature centrifugation or stochastic, "fracturing" cataracting behaviour—can lead to sub-optimal performance or total process failure. Failure to predict such behaviours can compromise the stability of material residence times and heat transfer rates or disrupt material mixing, potentially halting the production line and hindering the entire ISRU sequence.

Beyond their utility in process hardware, rotating drums provide a measurement platform for determining the dynamic rheological characteristics of granular materials. This utility is underscored by the recent adoption of rotating drum testers as a standardised methodology under ASTM D8648-25 (April 2026) (ATSM Standards, 2026), providing a benchmark for quantifying the flow properties of powders and granular solids.

2.2 Theory of Dynamic Granular Handling and Flow Regimes

Understanding the transitions between granular flow regimes is fundamental to the design of robust lunar materials handling systems. The rotating drum serves as a core geometry for investigating these dynamic behaviours, where the motion of the granular bed is primarily governed by the dimensionless Froude Number ($Fr = \omega^2 R / g$), representing the ratio of inertial to gravitational forces.

As rotational energy increases, the bulk material transitions through several distinct flow states (Govender, 2016):

- **Slumping and Rolling:** At low Froude numbers, the bed exhibits slumping, characterised by discrete, periodic avalanches or "bed fracturing" where the bulk yield stress is reached stochastically. As speed increases, the system enters the rolling regime. Here, a steady-state continuous surface layer forms, providing a stable shear environment where the material maintains a consistent profile.
- **Cascading and Cataracting:** Increasing rotational velocity introduces higher kinetic energy, causing the free surface to become S-shaped or curved as material cascades vigorously down the slope. At higher speeds, the regime shifts to cataracting, where particles are projected into ballistic trajectories, subsequently impacting the active layer and contributing to significant energy dissipation and potential comminution or bed dilation.
- **Centrifuging:** When the centrifugal acceleration matches or exceeds local gravity ($Fr \geq 1$), the material is pinned

against the drum wall. In this state, relative motion between particles ceases, and the bed rotates as a quasi-solid body.

The transition between these regimes is not purely a function of drum geometry; it is highly sensitive to inter-particle forces, including friction, cohesion, and electrostatic charge. In lunar-like environments (vacuum or low-gravity), these parameters shift significantly (Pawlowski et al., 2025). While a rotating drum allows for the determination of various metrics - such as the cohesive index, powder dilation, and thixotropy - the Dynamic Angle of Repose (θ_{dyn}) remains the primary descriptor for material handling performance (Fritz et al., 2009; Neveu et al., 2022).

The Dynamic Angle of Repose provides a direct macro-scale measurement of the internal resistance to flow under kinetic conditions. It captures the interplay between the material's physical properties (e.g., particle shape, angularity), environmental conditions (e.g., local gravity, atmospheric pressure, and moisture content), and the resulting inter-particle forces (e.g., cohesion, friction, and electrostatic charge). In this work, θ_{dyn} is used as the lead metric to characterise the rheological "fingerprint" of lunar regolith simulants and to compare the performance of the custom experimental breadboard against established commercial benchmarks.

2.3 Influence of the Lunar environment and Material Properties on Drum Performance

While terrestrial flow models are extensively documented, the lunar environment introduces variables that fundamentally alter granular dynamics. The most prominent factor is reduced gravity ($1/6g$), which significantly diminishes the self-weight of the regolith. While this reduction lowers vertical compaction stresses, it simultaneously weakens the gravitational restoring force that drives the downward phase of slumping and cascading motions. Consequently, inter-particle cohesive forces become increasingly significant relative to gravitational loads, shifting regime boundaries and increasing the likelihood for material adhesion or bulk clumping compared to terrestrial observations (Kleinhaus et al., 2011; Walton et al., 2007).

The absence of an atmosphere further modifies internal mechanics by eliminating interstitial gas effects. On Earth, the movement of air through a cascading bed can induce local fluidisation or aeration; however, in a lunar vacuum, these gas-driven pressure gradients are absent. In this state, the regolith operates in a free-molecular flow regime where the lack of atmospheric shielding eliminates gas-driven drag forces (Wylegała et al. 2026). Separately, the ultra-high vacuum environment preserves the chemical cleanliness of particle surfaces by preventing the adsorption of atmospheric species. This absence of adsorbed gas layers can amplify inter-particle friction and adhesive bonding. Furthermore, the high state of desiccation and the accumulation of electrostatic charges on regolith grains exacerbate cohesive interactions, making the resulting bed behaviour and flow regime transitions difficult to predict, including the potential for premature centrifugation at lower operational speeds.

The unique characteristics of lunar regolith are a direct consequence of this extreme environment. Formed through eons of space weathering - including micrometeoroid bombardment and solar wind exposure - the material consists of highly angular, irregularly shaped particles. These morphologies lack the rounding effects of terrestrial erosion, resulting in high internal friction and mechanical interlocking (Slyuta, 2014). Under vacuum, the absence of adsorbed gas layers further enhances these interactions, suggesting that the dynamic behaviour of lunar regolith will differ substantially from nominally similar materials on Earth.

Currently, no validated lunar regolith simulant realistically replicates these handling properties under the combined conditions of vacuum and reduced gravity. Furthermore, terrestrial samples of authentic lunar regolith are limited in quantity and subject to potential alteration through long-term storage or atmospheric exposure. Therefore, in-situ testing with naturally occurring lunar material under authentic environmental conditions is necessary to ultimately calibrate terrestrial simulants

and validate the predictive handling models required for future mission hardware.

2.4 Limitations of Existing Experimental Breadboards

Current breadboard designs for characterising the dynamic behaviour of lunar granular materials are often limited by significant operational overhead and low throughput. A primary constraint of these systems is the inability to evaluate multiple bulk material samples within a single experimental cycle without manual intervention. Sequential testing typically necessitates the physical disassembly and reloading of the rotating drum assembly or the deployment of redundant units, which substantially increases the mass and volume of the experimental payload. These constraints render existing breadboards impractical for use within vacuum chambers and especially during time-constrained reduced-gravity parabolic flight campaigns (Kleinhans et al., 2011; Williams et al., 2008).

To address these limitations, a pragmatic, two-stage development approach was adopted. In this work, a verification breadboard (Version A) was designed to validate core mechanical and electronic performance under vacuum conditions and to "de-risk" the system architecture. Experimental data collected from this breadboard were directly compared against standardised measurements from a commercially available rotating drum tester.

It is intended that follow-on work will focus on the development of a breadboard Version B. Built on the same dimensional platform, this upgraded iteration will incorporate an automated carousel-based dosing device to allow multiple samples to be autonomously filled into and emptied from a suitably modified rotating drum assembly. This configuration is designed to enable high-throughput data acquisition during parabolic flights and vacuum chamber testing, meeting the requirements for future lunar payload missions

2.5 Commercial Benchmark: The GranuDrum System

Standardised rotating drum testers are currently available as Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) systems for the routine characterisation of dynamic bulk material properties, including the dynamic angle of repose, angle of first avalanche, cohesive index, and roughness index. A prominent example is the GranuDrum tester produced by Granutools (Granutools, 2026).

The internal dimensions of the rotating drum in our experimental breadboard were specifically selected to match those of the GranuDrum tester, ensuring direct comparability of results. However, a significant limitation of the standard GranuDrum system is its reliance on manual disassembly for sample loading and its lack of compatibility with high-vacuum environments. To address these measurement requirements with the constraints of vacuum testing and the need for portability, a custom experimental breadboard was developed, the design and manufacture of which are detailed in the following section.

3 Design and Manufacture of a Vacuum-Compatible Rotating Drum Breadboard

3.1 Introduction

Breadboard Version A represents the first stage in the development of the rotating drum experimental platform. It was designed to validate the core mechanical and electronic architecture while demonstrating the capability to generate

dynamic granular material handling data comparable to standardised commercial testers. The system is capable of characterising sample properties under vacuum conditions across a wide range of rotational speeds (RPM). In this initial version, sample loading and removal are performed manually, necessitating the re-establishment of vacuum conditions following each sample exchange.

The successful verification of these core design solutions is the prerequisite for the subsequent development of Breadboard Version B. As discussed in Section 2.4, that future iteration will integrate the automated sample handling and multi-sample carousel capabilities required for high-throughput autonomous operation during parabolic flight campaigns and eventual deployment as a lunar surface payload. The remainder of Section 3 focuses specifically on the design requirements, manufacture, and functional verification of the Version A platform.

3.2 Breadboard Design Requirements

The design requirements for the breadboard were driven by the constraints of the test environments - vacuum chambers and parabolic flight platforms - and the necessity for appropriate data acquisition. Although Version A uses manual sample exchange, its architecture was required to accommodate future upgrades to the autonomous Version B configuration.

- **Operational Requirements:** The system must be fully compatible with vacuum environments to suppress atmospheric drag and fluidisation effects. This necessitates the use of materials and pre-treatments that minimise outgassing.
- **Functional Requirements:** To investigate distinct flow regimes, the rotating drum must be remotely or autonomously operated over a range of rotational speeds while inside a vacuum.
- **Physical and Interface Requirements:** The system must fit within a compact vacuum assembly suitable for transport. The authors used an Applied Vacuum Engineering (AVE) VC-12VF glass cylinder (301 mm ID, 356 mm height) vacuum chamber (Applied Vacuum Engineering Ltd., 2026), supported by an Agilent TPS-mini turbomolecular pump (Agilent Technologies Inc., 2026) and a Pirani/Penning pressure gauge combination. Integrated lighting and recording equipment must reside within the vacuum chamber, eliminating the need for complex external optical setups and representing features of an eventual lunar flight model. Finally, the drum dimensions must remain consistent with commercial standards (e.g., GranuDrum, 80 mm diameter, 20 mm depth) to ensure the validity of comparative datasets.

3.3 Design and Manufacture of the Version A Breadboard

Version A was designed for autonomous operation during experimental runs via a computer-controlled stepper motor. While sample loading and unloading remain manual, the rotational sequences and video acquisition are fully automated. The assembly was manufactured using a balance of Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM) 3D printing and CO₂ laser cutting for structural components, supplemented by Commercial-Off-The-Shelf (COTS) mechanical and electronic parts to ensure a cost-effective build (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Presentation of the rotating drum experimental breadboard: (a) CAD representation of the experimental rotating drum breadboard emphasising key features with translucent rear drum face (in purple), main drum body of 80 mm internal diameter (in green), transparent front drum face, stepper motor (in blue), LED lighting ring (in red), and video camera (in orange); (b) experimental drum breadboard; (c) experimental drum breadboard inside a vacuum chamber with internal diameter of 301 mm and with a regolith simulant in the drum and the LED lighting ring back illuminating the sample through the translucent rear drum face; (d) commercial GranuDrum tester with 80 mm diameter drum (copyright: Granutools). The self-contained, cable-free architecture is an important design feature intended to simplify integration within vacuum chambers.

3.3.1 General Description

The entire assembly is sized to fit within the specified AVE vacuum chamber (Figure 1c). To avoid the complexity of vacuum feedthroughs, the stepper motor, control electronics, power supply, and Wi-Fi data transfer unit are housed directly on the breadboard structure. This renders the breadboard completely autonomous in terms of power and data transfer, allowing it to function without external electrical or data cabling through the chamber walls.

3.3.2 Rotating Drum Construction

Structural components were FDM 3D printed using Polyethylene Terephthalate Glycol (PETG) (Prusament PETG, Prusa Research) with 100% infill. This approach was chosen to minimise vacuum outgassing; PETG exhibits lower water absorption than other common FDM polymers, and the solid infill prevents the formation of air-filled internal voids that could act as "virtual leaks" during pump-down. The transparent front window was laser-cut from 1.0 mm clear polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA).

The drum dimensions (80 mm internal diameter, 20 mm internal depth) were chosen to match the commercial GranuDrum instrument (Figure 1d). The translucent rear window of the drum,

facilitating back-illumination, was FDM 3D printed using white PLA. While PETG would have been preferred, its mass was negligible enough that PLA did not compromise chamber testing. The support structure and drum were assembled using stainless steel screws self-threaded into appropriately sized 3D-printed pilot holes.

The drum is driven by a NEMA 14 hybrid bipolar stepper motor providing a holding torque of 650 g-cm. An aluminium mounting hub adaptor allowed for the rapid removal of the drum for emptying and filling. The motor is controlled by a TMC2209 driver utilising proprietary StealthChop™ technology to minimise vibrations that might affect granular flow behaviour.

3.3.3 Illumination, Video Recording, and Control

Back-illumination of the drum is provided by a 16-element RGB LED ring set to maximum white brightness. Positioned behind the drum, this produces high-contrast silhouettes of the granular bed, facilitating automated video analysis of handling behaviour.

Imaging is performed using a Raspberry Pi (RPi) Camera Module 3 operated in manual mode. Videos are captured at 60 FPS (1024x1024 pixels) with a 1.5 ms exposure time. A Raspberry Pi 5 Single Board Computer (SBC) manages the

hardware interface and video recording via a custom Python script.

To power the system, a Waveshare UPS (E) HAT utilising four 21700 lithium-ion cells was integrated. To prevent thermal runaway in the absence of convective cooling inside the vacuum chamber, an autonomous thermal duty cycle was implemented. The system utilised the RPi SBC Power Management IC (PMIC) and Real-Time Clock (RTC) to enter a low-thermal-output deep-sleep state during prolonged pump-down phases, waking briefly to check for user intervention. Upon achieving the target vacuum pressure, the user could intercept the sleep-wake cycle from an external PC to initiate the measurement protocol; otherwise, the system automatically returned to deep sleep to maintain thermal safety.

4 Rotating drum breadboard testing in atmospheric and vacuum conditions in 1g

4.1 Introduction

This section details the functional testing and demonstration of the rotating drum breadboard under both atmospheric and vacuum conditions at 1g. The primary objective is to validate the breadboard's performance by directly comparing its output with data produced by a commercially available, standardised laboratory tester (GranuDrum) across a broad range of planetary regolith simulants and observed flow regimes.

4.2 Description of the test protocol

To facilitate a direct comparison with the standardised laboratory tester, the breadboard procedure was designed to mimic the standard test protocol of the GranuDrum rotating drum tester for determining the dynamic angle of repose at various rotational speeds. After filling the drum with 55 mL of granular sample (approximately 50% of the total internal volume), a measurement sequence involving a stepwise increase and decrease in rotational speed was implemented. This began with several seconds of high-speed rotation to achieve initial mixing before allowing the bed to settle. The sequence then proceeded from 2 RPM through 4, 6, 8, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, and 60 RPM, before reversing in the same order. Each speed was maintained for 20 seconds to allow the flow regime to develop and stabilise. These increments enabled the identification of distinct flow regimes—ranging from slumping and rolling to cascading, cataracting, and centrifuging.

Recording the sequence in reverse order enabled the detection of hysteresis effects (the difference in the dynamic angle of repose between the increasing and decreasing speed legs). Each sample was tested in triplicate, with the entire procedure video-recorded using the integrated camera and lighting system described in Section 3. The same protocol, as one of a number of pre-set options, was employed for the GranuDrum testing.

4.3 Planetary regolith simulants

Nine diverse regolith simulant samples were used for testing:

- JSC Mars-1: General-purpose Martian regolith simulant (Allen et al., 1997).
- NU-LHT-2M, TUBS-T, LHS-1: Lunar highland simulants (Linke et al., 2020; Long-Fox et al., 2022; Zeng et al., 2010).
- TUBS-M, EAC-1, LMS-1: Lunar mare simulants (Engelschön et al., 2020; Linke et al., 2020; Yin et al., 2023).
- LSP-2: Lunar South Pole simulant (Easter et al., 2024).
- Wood Flour: Representing reduced particle density simulants (Supreme Products, 2026).

The simulants were chosen to represent a broad range of lunar regions (mare, highlands, and South Pole). JSC Mars-1 provided a Martian analogue, while Wood Flour was used specifically to investigate the reduced particle density lunar regolith simulant paradigm (Pratnekar et al., 2025). These materials possess varied physical properties and flow characteristics, making them appropriate candidates for

evaluating the breadboard's sensitivity across a broad rheological spectrum.

4.4 Atmospheric and vacuum testing

Atmospheric testing comparing the breadboard and the GranuDrum was conducted at the European Space Agency's (ESA) Advanced Manufacturing Laboratory (Harwell Campus, UK). This controlled laboratory environment ensured consistent ambient temperature and relative humidity. To ensure statistical robustness, each simulant was evaluated in triplicate across both testing platforms.

Vacuum environment testing was performed at Cranfield University's Space Group Laboratory using an Applied Vacuum Engineering (AVE) vacuum chamber coupled with an Agilent TPS-mini turbomolecular pump system. Vacuum chamber pressure data were logged at a rate of 1 Hz throughout the experimental runs.

4.5 Preparation and analysis of the data

For the breadboard experimental runs, dynamic angle of repose values for each drum rotation speed were determined by manually selecting video frames from the captured files. These frames were visually enhanced to enable precise manual determination of the angle using ImageJ software. While manual determination was employed for this initial validation stage, future iterations (Version B) will incorporate automated video analysis.

For the samples analysed with the GranuDrum tester, the instrument's inbuilt automated video analysis provided the angle of repose values for each rotation speed directly.

4.6 Experimental (test) objectives

The primary objectives for the Version A breadboard tests were to:

- Verify operational capabilities: Prove that the breadboard functions mechanically and electrically in both atmospheric and vacuum environments.
- Confirm comparability: Ensure that results from the experimental breadboard are comparable with the industry-standard GranuDrum tester.
- Confirm behavioural sensitivity: Demonstrate that the breadboard can observe a range of granular material behaviours relevant to lunar research, including differences between simulants, pre-treatments (pre-baked vs. non-pre-baked), and environmental conditions (atmosphere vs. vacuum).

4.7 Results of rotating drum breadboard testing

4.7.1 *De-risking breadboard operation in various conditions*

Initial de-risking of Version A focused on laboratory atmospheric functionality. Mechanical assessments verified sample loading procedures, drum sealing, and appropriate drum rotation speeds and smoothness. Electrical checks confirmed reliable performance of the stepper motor, LED backlighting, and the Raspberry Pi's data management capabilities.

Subsequent trials focused on reaching target vacuum conditions (2×10^{-4} mbar). This pressure level represents a transition into a molecular flow regime relevant to lunar applications. A significant challenge was outgassing from the PETG structure, electronic components, and simulant volatiles. Although PETG was printed with 100% infill, outgassing persisted. Consequently, a vacuum pre-treatment protocol was implemented: the hardware was pre-baked for 12 hours at 50 °C in a vacuum oven, while simulants were pre-baked for 14 hours at 60 °C. Following this, example vacuum levels of 6×10^{-4} mbar for JSC Mars-1 and the required 2×10^{-4} mbar for EAC-1 were achieved within 180 minutes. This pump-down timeframe is acceptable for future parabolic flight campaigns where hardware is often prepared and pumped down prior to flight.

Thermal management was the final challenge. In a vacuum, the absence of convection increases the risk of thermal overload.

The autonomous thermal duty cycle (Section 3.3.3) successfully mitigated this, maintaining temperatures within safe limits through scheduled deep-sleep phases. The breadboard demonstrated complete operational reliability under both atmospheric and vacuum molecular flow conditions.

4.7.2 Comparison between Breadboard Version A and GranuDrum

A primary validation objective was ensuring that the experimental breadboard could physically replicate the granular dynamics observed in industry-standard instruments. Figure 2

provides qualitative evidence of this, showcasing the broad spectrum of flow regimes ranging from slumping and rolling to cascading, cataracting, and centrifuging successfully induced and recorded by the breadboard across various simulants and rotation speeds. The identification of these distinct physical transitions confirms that the hardware is inducing representative granular bed motion, providing an appropriate experimental dataset suitable for quantitative analysis.

Figure 2: Different flow regimes observed with different tested materials in rotating drum experimental breadboard. The image is arranged in 4 columns with each column showing different examples of one of four types of flow regimes. The names of the flow regimes are given across the top of the image and the regolith simulant used in each example is labeled below each image. All images are frames taken from video recordings and all examples are in the presence of 1 atmosphere pressure. The circle of white “dots” towards the centre of the drum is reflections of the LED lighting ring for the intermediate version of the breadboard before the LED lighting ring was moved behind the drum for back illumination that produced videos with high contrast more suited to future automated video analysis

With the qualitative functionality of the breadboard established, a quantitative comparison was performed to evaluate data comparability with the GranuDrum. The results for the nine regolith simulants are presented in Figure 3. To facilitate a concise visual comparison of these large datasets, Figure 3 uses grey bars to represent the total observed range of the dynamic angle of repose (θ_{dyn}) for each material, encompassing both the increasing and decreasing rotational speed sequences as separate bars. Individual data points are overlaid on these bars, with dot colour intensity shifting from light (2 RPM) to dark (60 RPM), enabling the simple identification of speed-dependent trends and potential hysteresis effects.

Visual inspection of Figure 3 indicates that the experimental breadboard demonstrates comparability with the standardised GranuDrum tester across all test materials. For free-flowing simulants such as JSC Mars-1, LMS-1, and LSP-2, both platforms report consistent absolute ranges and clustered speed sequences. More importantly, the breadboard accurately replicated complex rheological “fingerprints,” such as the inverse relationship (higher angles at lower speeds) observed in cohesive highlands simulants like NU-LHT-2M and the TUBS series. While minor variations exist—likely due to the manual versus automated data extraction methods—the breadboard successfully captures the unique flowability, stability, and internal friction characteristics of each

material. These preliminary results conclude that the custom breadboard provides valid, comparable data to an ASTM-standardised system, confirming its suitability for further

development of and research with the breadboard in lunar-relevant environments.

Figure 3: Dynamic Angle of Repose for tested samples with breadboard and GranuDrum rotating drum tester at atmospheric pressure. Individual data points represent the dynamic angle of repose at specific rotating speeds, with dot colour intensity shifting from light (low RPM) to dark (high RPM). Grey bars indicate the observed range of values, enabling comparison between simulants, platforms, and RPM increasing and decreasing sequences

4.7.3 Demonstration of dynamic handling behaviour

Beyond general comparability, an important objective was to demonstrate that the custom breadboard is sensitive to the nuanced physical behaviours relevant to lunar research. While the current dataset is relatively limited and causal links remain speculative at this stage, the stark differences in observed behaviours and the high degree of repeatability across both independent measurement platforms are noteworthy. Characterisation of material-specific rotational trends in Figure 3 reveals distinct rheological "fingerprints" shared by both platforms. For example, simulants such as JSC Mars-1, LMS-1, and LSP-2 exhibit lower dynamic angles at low RPM which subsequently rise proportionally with rotational speed. This positive correlation is hypothesised to result from inertia-driven bed dilation, where increasing drum RPM (and thus the Froude Number, Fr) expands the active layer and permits the material to sustain steeper slopes before collapsing.

Conversely, cohesive simulants like NU-LHT-2M, TUBS-T, and EAC-1 exhibit a complete reversal of this trend, showing the highest angles at low RPM followed by a smooth gradual decrease as speed increases. This inverse relationship suggests a cohesion-dominated state at low energy levels (low Fr) where van der Waals forces and mechanical interlocking between irregular particle surfaces predominate; as rotational energy increases, it likely disrupts these cohesive structures to promote more fluid-like cascading. Finally, materials such as Wood Flour and LHS-1 appear more chaotically ranged as a function of RPM. This variability likely stems from unstable transitions between flow regimes or "stick-slip" behaviour, where the material's specific particle size distribution or lower particle density leads to stochastic avalanching rather than a steady-state profile.

Secondly, the breadboard demonstrated sensitivity to subtle rheological changes induced by material pre-treatment. The first part of Figure 4 (left) compares the dynamic angle of repose for TUBS-M in its "as-received" atmospheric state versus a thermally pre-treated state (pre-baked for 180 minutes at 80 °C). In both the breadboard and the GranuDrum, a visual shift is observed: the position of the bars for the dried sample shifts toward lower dynamic angle values. This trend is consistent with the suggestion that removal of moisture-driven capillary bonding, which reduces inter-particle cohesion, enhances material flowability and reduces the measured dynamic angle of repose (Lumay et al., 2016). The observation that the breadboard replicates this subtle shift observed in the industry-standard instrument confirms its use as a characterisation tool.

Finally, the breadboard's unique capability to operate under vacuum conditions (a feature not available on the GranuDrum) allowed for the detection of environmental sensitivity. The second part of Figure 4 (right) illustrates the transition from atmospheric to vacuum conditions for JSC Mars-1 and EAC-1. While JSC Mars-1 remained relatively stable, EAC-1 exhibited a distinct visual difference in results, with dynamic angle of repose values increasing significantly in a vacuum (Espiritu et al., 2020; Wylęgała et al., 2026). This suggests that for smaller, lighter particles like those in EAC-1, the transition to vacuum removes the subtle fluidisation or aeration effects provided by interstitial gas at atmospheric pressure, which otherwise act to reduce internal friction. The absence of these gas-mediated interactions likely allows inherent inter-particle forces and mechanical interlocking to dominate the granular dynamics, leading to the observed increase in flow resistance. The breadboard's ability to record this distinct environmental transition confirms its value for de-risking future lunar payloads by providing a valid platform for studying regolith dynamics in lunar-like molecular flow regimes.

Figure 4: Dynamic Angle of Repose measurements for thermally pre-treated and atmospheric conditioned regolith simulants and tests performed in vacuum environmental conditions. The left side of the figure demonstrates sensitivity to thermal pre-treatment using TUBS-M, where removal of moisture-driven capillary bonding results in a measurable decrease in flow resistance across both testing platforms. The right side of the figure illustrates the environmental transition from atmospheric to vacuum conditions, highlighting a significant increase in the dynamic angle of repose for finer-grained materials like EAC-1

4.8 Summary

The testing phase successfully provided an initial validation of the Version A breadboard as an appropriate research tool, demonstrating mechanical and electronic performance across both atmospheric and vacuum conditions. Quantitative comparisons confirmed that results are comparable to industry-standard equipment, while the system’s sensitivity to behavioural shifts—driven by material type, thermal pre-treatment, and the transition to molecular flow regimes—demonstrates its utility for de-risking future lunar material handling architectures.

5 Future Development of an Autonomous Multi-Sample Breadboard (Version B)

5.1 Automated breadboard design

The next developmental step, as previously outlined, is the design of an autonomous rotating drum breadboard (Version B) featuring a multi-sample dosing device and an automated system for filling and emptying test samples. Adopting a design philosophy similar to a previously developed reconfigurable wedge hopper breadboard by the same core authors (submitted for publication), this version will allow for the sequential testing of multiple samples within a vacuum chamber without repressurisation or manual human intervention between tests.

5.2 Automatic breadboard for lunar gravity parabolic flights

The automation and multi-sample capability is required for operating the rotating drum breadboard inside a vacuum chamber during a reduced-gravity parabolic flight campaign (Klein et al., 1990; Kleinhans et al., 2011). Parabolic flights offer sustained periods of lunar gravity (approximately 25–35 seconds per parabola) with roughly 30 parabolas per flight. This duration is sufficient to execute each key operational stage: drum filling, measurement at varied rotational speeds, and drum emptying.

Using the multi-sample carousel capacity of Version B, it would be possible to characterise up to seven different regolith simulants in a single flight under continuous vacuum conditions. In Europe, these campaigns are typically managed by the European Space Agency (ESA) in collaboration with Novaspace, utilising an A310 ZERO-G aircraft (Novaspace, 2026) to provide a three-day, three-flight campaign.

5.3 Protocol and experimental throughput for parabolic flight campaigns

On a typical flight day, 30 parabolas are performed in six sets of five parabolas. It is evident that the limited duration of reduced gravity does not permit the full test protocol outlined in Section 4.2; therefore, a level of data acquisition identical to laboratory standards is not feasible. Consequently, a streamlined experimental test protocol must be developed to ensure the delivery of relevant data within these constraints. The following options are pragmatic compromises:

Option A:

- 1st Parabola: Filling the rotating drum geometry with the granular material sample.
- 2nd Parabola: Performing dynamic material handling tests at a constant rotational speed.
- 3rd Parabola: Releasing the granular material from the rotating drum.

This option enables 10 individual samples to be tested in a single flight day. However, under the current design, the dosing device is limited to 7 individual samples. While performing a test run at a single speed for 25–30 seconds would allow the granular flow to fully develop, the experimental output would be limited in terms of data diversity, as measurements across different RPMs would be missing.

Option B:

- 1st Parabola: Filling the rotating drum with the granular sample.
- 2nd Parabola: A sequence of low-medium-high RPM increments (10 seconds each).
- 3rd Parabola: Repetition of the low-medium-high RPM sequence (10 seconds each).
- 4th Parabola: Repetition of the low-medium-high RPM sequence (10 seconds each).
- 5th Parabola: Releasing the granular material.

Option B also allows for the testing of up to six different samples in a single 30-parabola flight. The primary benefit of this strategy is the internal replication of measurements within a single flight, enabling a three-day campaign to test more than six sample types while providing necessary contingency for unexpected results.

While each proposed option involves trade-offs regarding data variation across rotational speeds, both are capable of delivering meaningful experimental results and remain compatible with the current carousel-type dosing device design, which accommodates up to seven individual samples.

An important caveat of parabolic flight testing is that the short reduced-gravity phases are interleaved with short periods of hypergravity. This cyclic transition is an inherent part of each parabola and will impart a brief consolidation stress on the regolith sample between experimental reduced gravity steps.

6 Conclusion

This study outlined the design, manufacture, and testing of an experimental rotating drum breadboard (Version A), specifically tailored for operation within a vacuum chamber.

The system successfully demonstrated the functionality of its mechanical and electronic components under both atmospheric and vacuum conditions. Furthermore, the performance of the proposed drum was directly compared with standardised, commercially available rotating drum equipment. The acquired data, in the form of measured dynamic angles of repose for nine different test materials, indicated comparability between the two platforms. The breadboard was subsequently used for further

testing of lunar regolith simulants under various pre-treated conditions and across atmospheric and vacuum environments. The results aligned with expectations for the specific material types and environmental conditions investigated.

By addressing the primary design and validation objectives of this phase, this experimental breadboard will serve as an appropriate testbed for designing a more advanced, multi-sample, fully autonomous version (Version B). This next iteration will be capable of operating within a vacuum chamber during reduced-gravity parabolic flights without the need for human intervention. Ultimately, this work - as part of the overarching MULE Project framework - is intended to facilitate the development of a dedicated lunar surface payload or subsystem. By generating in situ datasets using lunar materials within the lunar environment, such an implementation would provide the definitive "ground truth" necessary to validate or update our understanding of lunar material handling, thereby de-risking the technologies, processes, and architectures that will be underpinned by this knowledge.

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